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Management Summary

Mobile B2E apps are evolving issues when it comes to the implementation of new technologies in business organisation, delivering innovative services for several operations involving the customers and companies. For companies that have included such a mobile app within the project scope, the requirements elicitation process plays a vital role in determining the requirements and to build a foundation for the next or subsequent long-term decisions. This study presents an offer for a B2E company in the food sector with the aim of finding out the requirements for the project. The introduced approach employs tested and ascertained methods and analysis from the of project management and software development fields

The study covers an evaluation of three vital groups of requirements (Functional, Structural and Resources). In order to determine the functionalities the B2E app will deliver, the methods stakeholder and market analysis are presented. For the structural requirements, the risk assessment and system environment analysis, were presented. Lastly, for resources requirements, the project time planning and life-cycle cost analysis were presented. The full study is scheduled to be completed within 6 months which is broken down into 24 weeks and well illustrated by the Gantt-chart. The contribution segment admits the benefits of the methods selected, their importance and the reasons why they were employed in the study. The information and vital results from this study enables the client to take the decision whether it worth it to continue with development of the mobile app itself or not,

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Chapter 1: Introduction- Background and Objectives

Background of the Study

The introduction of innovative technologies for communication brings about along new avenues of transacting business operations daily. The internet has intensely influenced how business and customers communicate. Mobile devices in the contemporary business environment have become a pivotal point in diverse sectors, for example in Financial Institutions, Restaurants, Hotels, Travel Providers, Education, etc. Companies in these sectors have perceived mobile apps in Mobile devices to be an excellent avenue to improve both sales and brand performance for their businesses. The advent of mobile app for business has made it possible for consumers to buy and sell goods and services via their smartphones.

Mobile application (app) is an electronic platform where people can interact and transact business via electronic devices such as smartphones, tablets, computer etc. It has given companies a new look of how businesses can be done. It is increasingly becoming a strong medium for consumers to gain more access to certain information about goods and services provided by the company and also be able do their shopping conveniently online (Vijayan and Raju, 2011). Mobile apps is become very paramount among both large and small businesses in today's world (Kakkar, Shah and Kakkar (2013). It is an essential platform of digital interaction not just for Business-to-Consumer (B2C) market but also Business-to-Enterprise (B2E) which helps to target business to enterprise activities such as supply-chain management, e-payment and e-procurement (Al-Naeem et al., 2005). B2E applications has evolved as a vital tool that drive customer relationship management (Smilansky, 2015). Kapil (2017) points out that most successful companies are maximising the benefits of mobile apps to achieve different business goals.

The present client, who is a Small and Medium enterprise (SME) in food sector providing food products to catering companies is aware of this development and intends to create and implement a B2E app for their customers to use but this intended development is not within the company's specialism. Moreover, considering the high complexity that is involve in this kind of information communication technology (ICT) projects, there is need for an in-depth study as Azadegan et al. (2013) points out in order to bring out the collective requirements so

as to avoid a failed project. Thus, the need to carry out a scoping study to determine the essential requirements for developing the mobile app is very vital.

Gunda (2008) regarded requirements elicitation as the vital step in determining software development, thus, this study will take on the requirement elicitation method where different stakeholders of the intended business app will be analysed along with their needs. As Goel & Kulkarni, (2017) also noted that the success of most project regarding software development relies strongly on the quality of requirements identified and the methods applied to gather them. Getting the right data is critical to understand how the mobile app will fit into the B2E environment and the different project requirements.

Since this is a project, project management methods and case studies from software development projects will play a vital role in presenting the requirements. Organization wide and industry based assessment research will also be used to analyze and justify the methods used and provide important information essential for the content of the app. This study shall provide valuable information about different project necessities. This report being a consulting task will uncover and acquire expounding requirements via the functional, structural and resource requirements with respect to the development of the app. These also serve as the objectives to the study where the objectives build upon one another.

Objectives of the Study

Objective 1

To examine the functional requirements of mobile Business-to-Enterprise (B2E) application for catering companies within the food industry. This objective will be achieved using the:

- Stakeholder Mapping
- Market Analysis

Objective 2

To identify the structural requirements involve in programming and implementing the app within the current structure and competences of the company. This objective will be achieved by engaging in:

- Risk assessment analysis

- System Environmental analysis

Objective 3

To determine the necessary resources requirements for the clients' company to be able to program, implement and operate successfully the B2E app. This objective will be achieved by employing:

- Project time planning
- Life-cycle cost analysis

At the onset, the report will demonstrate the intended suitable methods required with the aim to disclose the specific requirements of the stated objectives. Subsequently, the methods are explained, whereas supporting evidences from academic literature related to project management illustrate the suitability of the methods used. Furthermore, the report presented with the aid of a Gantt chart the requirements showing the methods, activities and time needed for each key task. Then, the contribution of the specific methods and the project as a whole will expound on benefits of the adopted method and why it is the most beneficial for the company goals. In conclusion, the final observations will summarise the focal points so as to deliver final presumption to this report.

Chapter 2: Supportive Evidence

This section aims at providing an all-inclusive research method for the client which includes all the essential requirements so as to evaluate what it takes to develop a B2E app for their company. It also examines the context and the individual processes with respect to particular approach adopted for the study. It is vital to state that gathering the necessary information or data for the proposed methods need two-way communication system with the client. Thus, there should be room for changing and updating the client requirements during the whole requirements elicitation process and when identified, they should be integrated into the

project. This notion stems from the works of Houdek and Pohl (2000) with respect to Daimler-Chrysler projects where they evaluated the requirements elicitation process and asserted that more than 50% of the necessary requirements changes occurred after the real identification process. This justified why Rafiq et al. (2017) strongly recommended an open communicative exchange with client.

2.1 Objective 1 – Functional Requirements

The Functional Requirements examines the method and procedures needed to meet the requirements of the Clients. It deals with the relevant questions on how and what needs to be done i.e. how the mobile app will look to satisfy the stakeholders of the company and also what functional path (for example e-payment, supply-chain management, sales and marketing etc) the application will follow. The clients get the necessary information regarding what the stakeholders and market require of the B2E app.

2.1.1 Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholders are the persons or group of persons that has an interest and also impacted by it activities and decisions taken by a company. In project management, Stakeholder mapping or analysis is broadly used as an element of the functional requirements process which provides a wide-ranging information necessary for execution of a project (Alia and Abdelfettah, 2016). The stakeholders involved in the development of the B2E app are the persons or group of persons who impact and are impacted by the business app. This analysis poses to give answer to who are the vital stakeholders in this project, what are their likely needs and their level of importance in a stakeholder's map. It is also important to examine their conflicting expectations with regards to the new intended app.

In addition, Calvert (1995) proposed a brainstorming meeting for identifying and mapping the stakeholders for the client. In performing a detailed stakeholders mapping, both the internal and external stakeholders are identified in with the decision makers, investors, developers and users of the app from the onset to the completed lifecycle of app development. Thereafter, all the stakeholder would be engaged in a direct communication to determine their varying needs and requirements either via planned consultations or personal discussions. This approach ensures a proper stakeholder engagement from the beginning of

the project (Passenheim, 2009) which helps to analyse the stakeholders that need to be monitored, kept satisfied, managed closely and kept informed.

2.1.2 Market Analysis

Analysing the market is very important in order to understand the needs, expectations, or preferences of customers who are the users of the B2E app. It helps to determine the integration pathways of the app. For the successful implementation of the B2E application, it is very vital to conduct a market analysis for the Client's need so as to make right decisions. A comprehensive data of size of the target market and the trends of the food sector is critical to decide on how the application would be designed so as to be suitable and adapted to the market. The data will help app designers to evaluate size and future trends of the food sector and therefore able to develop the mobile app with unique marketing design and features.

In addition, it is very vital to research the market carefully and understand the profile of the target customers in order to apply user friendly and oriented approaches to the app design. If the mobile app designers are not able to understand the users of the app, then the mobile app fails to achieve its objectives by not representing such understanding in the designing process and, therefore, the prospect of accepting of this app decreases (Robertson, 2005). Moreover, the market analysis also offers an idea of the prevalent software and hardware that can support the mobile app and also examine the affordability and capability of customers to use the mobile app. In this case, the study will uncover the potential users of the app and their features so as to determine the level of transactions that can be made through the app. In addition, the market analysis is vital to explain to the stakeholders of project and show the benefits in order for the company to create a successful B2E app.

2.2 Objective 2 – Structural Requirements

The next objective deals with the structural requirements involved in creating and managing a successful B2E app. The structural requirement deals with the relevant questions outlining on how the B2E app would be implemented. It examines how clients satisfy the structural requirements to the program and implementation of the app match with the existing organisational environment. For example, risk assessments and system environmental analyses plays an essential role as a result of their impact on the subject matter whether the

client is able to proffer solution to the control deviations and likely risks or if need be to engage external bodies as an alternative.

Bpayne and Watt (2018) pointed out that there are three general types of non-functional development limitations which are resources, time and quality. These constraints are generally important to know the volume of the project requirements of a given software. The number is vital for evaluating the size of a change or alterations in project requirements, to estimate cost of development and maintenance task.

2.2.1 Risk Assessment Analysis

This segment of the structural requirements analysis involves identifying and assessing risk associated with the project. Passenheim (2009) noted that a thoroughly conducted risk management method is one of the key steps in preparing each project. Moreover, Kakkar, Shah and Kakkar (2013) expounded that risk identification and analysis are the foundation of risk management in software project development. The multifaceted nature of software development makes risk analysis a tough process, that needs comprehensive and detailed assessment. Each singular project comprises of risks which can be referred to as unplanned deviations from planned objectives of which, when they occur can impact a project positively or negatively (Vivian, 2016). While the complete eradication of risks is not likely, the general purpose is to identify, control and possibly mitigated the risks (Nicholas and Steyn, 2012). The risks in project risks can occur as a result of multiple elements and can happen at each stage of project (Lock, 2013). Maley (2012) also noted that they can either be based on external or internal factors. Thus, it is vital to identify as many risks as possible so as to prepare for the probable consequences.

Furthermore, the foundation of the risk identification stems from shared brainstorming with a documentation of the likely project risks of B2E applications (Maley, 2012). Besides, drawing experiences as suggested by Lock (2013) from previous projects of client have a potential to have an effect on the risk identification process. This process entails that each risk might someday have harmful consequences for the outcome of the project. When the risks are identified, they have to be assessed and analysed in order to deduce if the client would be able to deal with them. The likelihood of the risks and the level of impact plays significant roles in evaluating the project risks (Kakkar, Shah and Kakkar, 2013).

The evaluation in this case classifies the risk according to their impact level and thus ranked into a risk matrix based on the assessment (Passenheim, 2009). The consequences of these risks can vary from low to medium and to high depending on several factors, henceforth it is vital for the company to take into consideration the risks while developing the new mobile app (Kakkar, Shah and Kakkar, 2013). After identifying, evaluating and ranking the risk, a risk mitigation plan needs to be developed so as a likely solution to the consequences of the impact of the risks. The risk assessment analysis is also expected to ensure optimistic time and cost estimates, minimise unexpected or unprepared cost and also make sure all the stakeholder's inputs are taken into consideration (Liz, 2018).

2.2.2 System Environment Analysis

The system environment analysis serves as a strong foundation for analysis the of structural requirements. The segment of the structural requirements examines how “easy” or “difficult” it is to program and implement expected functions of the B2E mobile app within the scope of the client's system environment. This step is very important for the requirements elicitation process as a result of the need to surround the B2E app within the current system environment (MacLean et al., 2004). An IT infrastructure here entails the networking subsystems that are part of the functioning business (Singer et al., 2009). Surrounding changes within such an IT environment that includes other parties develops limitations that are vital as a result of the question if the client would be able deal with the limitations (MacLean et al., 2004).

Thus, the system environment analysis as suggested by Pries and Quigley (2008) has to include the identification of *current* systems, elements and interfaces (previously) and of *essential* systems, elements and interfaces (subsequently) among the new mobile app and current system environment. Additionally, it has to show current IT service, security, performance, memory storage and support processes which also have to be taken into consideration in the implementation of the B2E app. The basis of the system environment analysis draws strength by meeting and interviewing app developers and owners with the aim of getting an overview of the interrelated systems. In the case where the IT processes are managed by external provider it might be important to engage the provider as an additional source of information. The current system's manuals can also be consulted to collect relevant information (Vijayan and Raju, 2011).

Furthermore, on the basis of the gathering information, the IT environment need to be researched in order to analyse and documents needs so as to be able to assess how the new app will fit into the existing IT environment (Pries and Quigley, 2008). Analysing further the needs will reveal possible necessary element adoptions and determine which particular IT expertise are required to develop a successful app.

Furthermore, the software (mobile app) should be test run in IT environment in order to test and prepare for essential functionality and build structure for the app (Kakkar, Shah and Kakkar, 2013). The app should be tested on several available platform so proper working is done on all platform, that is several dimensions an app should function on devices with diverse screen sizes and resolution (Kakkar, Shah and Kakkar, 2013). Additionally, network related testing should be done also on all network so as to have some change in their proprieties. For example an app should be able deliver satisfactory behavior on the current model platform (4G).

2.3 Objective 3 – Resources Requirements

After examining the structural requirements for developing the mobile B2E app, the traditional project management planning techniques can be employed and conducted so as to determine the resources required that the client need to pool together. The resources required most likely are tangible in nature such as equipment, facilities, employees, or other quantifiable resources essential for the implementation of the project (Bpayne and Watt, 2018). Taking into consideration the example of the mobile app, this resources requirement analysis deals with questions of how long will it take to build the software to create the app and project timing of activities along with the analysis of relevant cost resources required to conduct the project.

2.3.1 Project Time Planning

The client's B2E software development project is just like any other project that involves individual steps that have to be undertaken. Project time planning analysis is a vital step to shows temporal requirements so as to get a complete view of the time the company need to spend for the entire project. Lock (2013) noted that time estimation portray a distinct problem because of the high difficulty and dependence on ambiguous reports especially in the case of

software developments projects. According Maroukian, K. (2010), project time planning anchors on manufacturing of an activity based network and the drawing of a Gantt chart. For this scoping study of the B2E mobile app, the Gantt chart is applicable and employed to help identify, define and breakdown the project activities and also estimate the activity duration and schedule (Lindholm and Suomala, 2005).

The preliminary phase towards the project time planning is to first of all break down the project into concrete activities so as to give a basis for time estimation and scheduling activities. This phase necessitates deeper knowledge and expertise in software development and testing measures, i.e. it relies on experienced software developers and also previous case studies that are relevant to estimating the timing required for all the activities (Korpi and Ala-Risku, 2008). After all activities (network-based) are identified, they have to be put in a logical order. The dependencies and singular task durations now permit for the drawing of network diagram, thereby taking into consideration each milestone along with the start times and end times. At the end, the network diagram results give a basis for a comprehensive Gantt chart (Passenheim, 2009). Additionally, MS Project which is a project management software can also be employed as it can provide several options for the client with respect to the outline of the time planning

2.3.2 Life-Cycle Cost Analysis

The segment of the resources requirements portrays the life-cycle cost analysis. This method of the resources requirements deals with questions of what is the cumulative or sum up costs for all activities that the client bear (Vlachy, 2014). It is used to identify and assess the total project cost and select the relevant activities with lowest cost possible. It also assess the economic impact of a product throughout its life cycle (Douglass, 2016). It is employed in the pre-project planning phase because it provides an initial overview over a long-term range. The life-cycle cost analysis examines cost such as direct and indirect, tangible and intangible and also the external costs (Norris, 2001). For example, it can be labour, material, or overhead cost. This method helps companies to make an investment decision that is cost-effective over the lifespan of the project.

However, with respect to developing an app, the software products have different life cycle phases with associated costs. Nevertheless, many costs incurred are not apparent without an proper analysis (Eckardt et al., 2014). Thus, life-cycle cost analysis appears to be a suitable

approach for the client's project since it covers pertinent programming and implementation costs along with the follow-up costs for instance the essential operating, maintenance and disposal costs, from the start to the termination of the project (Nicholas and Steyn, 2012). Moreover, this method is also important since these costs are connected with each other.

Furthermore, the outcome of the project time planning and its identified activities gives a first insight over the essential project steps. Abran (2015) opined that this process is buttressed by a software for estimation and calculations are based on market-based prices for hourly wages and needed software tools. Afterwards, the individual costs are collated and summed up, providing a report about the costs for the mobile app life-cycle. Nevertheless, the danger of life-cycle cost is that the data in some cases, may not be reliable because costs can change over time, and the analysis might not forestall possible changes (Higham et al., 2015). Thus, Passenheim (2009) suggested altering the costs during implementation stage based on more comprehensive and precise data, thereby improving the reliability.

Chapter 3: Study of Gantt-Chart

As aforementioned in the previous section, all the methods are linked by specific implementation phases and they show precise process durations. In this section, a Gantt chart is presented as a vital tool with the aim to give an overview of the processes and requirements involved in each stage of executing the project for client, consultant and key stakeholders (Nicholas and Steyn, 2012). The Gantt chart reflects different time and durations involved in implementation of the complete project stages and their dependencies. It depicts all the activities of the project along with the time frame for completion of each project task. It shows all the steps that have to be completed before the dependent and subsequent step can start (Passenheim, 2009)

The full study is scheduled to be completed within 6 months which is broken down into 24 weeks and commencing with an inception meeting to initiate the project. As previously mentioned, a continuous two-way communication between the client and consultant ensures study is robust, all-inclusive and sufficient. The inception meeting at the onset of the project introduces the stakeholders involved and the essential details with respect to the particular project phases as recommended by Passenheim (2009). The project phases align with each

objective and it is met by employing a suitable analytical tool. This is vital because it shows tasks to be completed and also their viability by displaying the activities in sequential order so as to achieve timely delivery of the whole project. The first 22 weeks entail the process of gathering relevant data in order to produce the draft of the report in week 23. In week 24 which is the last week, the final report will be presented to the client along with recommendations that may necessitate additional actions.

The Gantt chart in Figure 1 depicts the order of activity list, dependencies and timeframe. The task list aids to place and to allocate the dependencies. The task is undertaken when the cells are highlighted, which thus help the client and other stakeholders understand the key project phases, reach an agreement on expectations that the company expects from the consultancy project during the scheduled evaluation meeting meant for obtaining feedback and progress report. Nevertheless, because that most subsequent task builds on the previous, this makes the Gantt chart not to afford ample space for slack time. Notwithstanding, the project timeframes were projected widely so as to ensure there is no room for any significant delay. The client can harness the help of this Gantt-chart to track and evaluate project milestones and also identify the phase of the project where the client is so as to know what has been done and what is left within the timeframe specified (Zhang and Bishop, 2013).

Figure 1 – Project Gantt Chart (Author’s Design)

Chapter 4: Contribution

After putting together an overview of the methods and process for the study, this chapter focuses in details the question of how the each of the aforementioned methods in chapter 2 contribute to the objectives identified in implementing a mobile B2E app. The industry supportive based evidences and case studies from the software industry were combined with knowledge scholars gained employing the particular methods. Moreover, employing these methods will aid the client to make further critical decisions with respect to the project. If the discovered functional, structural and resources requirements don't fit to the client's competences, the client can consider outsourcing as an alternative to realising the project. Nevertheless, if the findings of the study revealed that taking up the project is within the client's competences, it would take a clue and guide from requirements elicitation for the mobile B2E app this study provides which would also help the client save money and time.

4.1 Objective 1: Functional Requirements

4.1.1 Stakeholder Mapping

The stakeholder mapping analysis will show a clear understanding of the needs of stakeholders with the aim of getting them involve in the business app project. To bring out the vital requirements elicitation for the app and ensure the quality of the software, Pacheco and Garcia (2012) suggests that the identification and understanding of the view of key stakeholders is very important. By identifying all key stakeholders, the mobile app can satisfactorily fulfil its value-based requirements, while Pan (2005) buttressed that understanding stakeholders and their objectives is vital so as not to abandon software development projects. Additionally, IT or software development project that does not involve the intended users can lead to a low level of interest or commitment and falling support for the project which is very vital for the success of the mobile app project.

Furthermore, performing a stakeholder mapping before embarking on the mobile app project would also help bring out imminent risks that can be harmful to the software project. Vrhovec et al. (2015) pointed that engaging stakeholder mapping analysis prior starting a software projects is linked strongly to risk assessment analysis process as a result of the related problems when the stakeholder needs are disregarded. Additionally, Rost and Glass (2009) stressed the need to analyse and assess stakeholders because of there vast experience,

exposure and coverage in the market which can be helpful to achieve an effective market analysis. This also allow for continuous improvement

4.1.2 Market Analysis

An effective market analysis with respect to the mobile B2E app will provide an understanding of the size, value and future trends of the mobile app for small business in the food sector. Rolstadas et al. (2015) pointed that market analysis adds value by improving project performance and success. Engaging in market analysis help to bring to light the market prospect for the new mobile app. Adetayo (2008) noted that many applications developed in the food sector don't provide a return on investment, because developers of the app don't consider certain market prospects vital for comprehensive analysis. Conducting the market analysis before developing the mobile app is a vital value creating approach that aids to determine the best features for the app that can ease interaction between customers and company's representative and deliver opportunities for supply-ordering and provide value to customers (Haugestad, 2015).

In addition, for this study, a market analysis which involves detailed data research will help provide relevant information about the end users of the app, exposure level to up-to-date technology and the specific level of application technology that matches their expectations (Jucan, 2013). All together, market analysis will spot out available market opportunities, pinpoint the B2E app criteria for success, needs of customers and market, and make known potential market risks.

4.2 Objective 2: Structural Requirements

4.2.1 Risk Assessment Analysis

Risk assessment analysis bring to limelight the associated risks and proffer how the client can deal with them via a developed mitigation plan. The analysis likewise is also important due to the high-risk vulnerability of software development projects the client intends to enter in (Zamfiroiu, 2015). By identifying and analysing the risks, the company would be able to group the elaborated requirements and to assess whether they are able to deal with the risks single-handedly. Drawing from industry based case study experience, where a full risk management framework is applied for a software development project for example in the Barbados government sector, Dey et al. (2007) buttressed that risk assessment analysis at the onset of

a software project portrays a requirement for making sure there is a clear understanding and comprehension of the risks and the necessary actions may be required to manage and mitigate those risks.

Thus, the approach will provide an elaborate list of the relevant risks of B2E app and the contingency plan required to assess the competences the company needs to develop so as to manage the risks in the project. Kakkar, Shah and Kakkar (2013) classified the risk in mobile app development into customer related, communication related, financial, market and external risks. Hence, it is important for the company to take into consideration these risks while developing the new mobile app so as to prepare any unplanned occurrence. Kapp and Girmscheid (2005) points that failed software development projects are often associated with risk management framework that is not inclusive and detailed. Hence, it is high importance for the company to obtain a comprehensive risk and required mitigation plan so to be able to harness the potential of modern B2E app suitable for SMEs.

4.2.2 System Environment Analysis

With respect to the new B2E mobile app for the company, the system environmental analysis helps to assess whether the new app will fit into the existing IT environment (Kapp and Girmscheid, 2005). It allows for conclusions about the risk assessment analysis as a new app may necessitate a new need for employees and skill sets of the IT personnel may leads to new risks. In addition, examining from the innovation system standpoint, this method is suitable because it has the capability to assess the factors that influence the Company to adopt new IT along with potential challenges in respect to the new system needs (Kaur and Sengupta,2011). Additionally, the system environment analysis allows for more deductions with respect to the requirements of the IT security, customer service management and risk management. A proper system environment analysis of software development projects helps avoid failed project of SMEs and also large companies as it takes cares of inadequate adaptions as well as other IT problems (Charette, 2005). If these problems are left ignored, they can lead to a fall in profits (Hazzan and Dubinsky, 2007).

4.3 Objective 3: Resource Requirements

4.3.1 Project Time Planning

Project time planning helps to determine how the investment of company's scarce resources could be used to develop a business app for small business that is suitable for customers' use, by identifying the breakdown of relevant project activities and estimation of time needed to achieve them (Firesmith, 2004). Additionally, in assessing the resources requirements for the new app, project time planning plays a significant purpose for the company by reason of several problems that happen over time. Problems such as wrong time estimates, project delays, and bottlenecks can cause time pressure and even late delivery, that affects the project costs negatively (Loo , 2003).

Zowghi and Coulin (2005) also demonstrated the importance of a proper project time planning method for the accurate estimation of temporal requirements even as software development project estimation is mostly not a precise science, yet proper scheduling is a right step towards minimising uncertainty in projects. Moreover, Verner, Evanco & Cerpa (2007) in their study of schedule estimation and success of software development project revealed that wrong time planning led to inadequate requirements, which was as a result of project time constraints. In this vein, it is very imperative to analyse and estimate the time in a logical order so as to prevent bad time planning and related risks and losses.

4.3.2 Life-Cycle Cost Analysis

The life-cycle cost analysis helps to identify total cost for the mobile app and also determine the economic impact of the app throughout its life cycle. Life-cycle cost analysis is one of the best methods used to evaluate the overall project's costs alternatives so as to be able to choose a suitable design that guarantees the lowest sum costs that is consistent with the project quality and purpose (Korpi and Ala-Risku, 2008). In employing the life-cycle cost in a software engineering project, Pan (2005) opined that the method is very all-inclusive and thorough used to assessed the costs of company's product from the beginning to the end of the life cycle. Thus, employing it at the conception stage for this new mobile app can serve as a strategic tool for managers to make effective decisions. Additional, the method reveals if the client would be able to gather all the required resources needed for the development of the mobile app.

Furthermore, in the software development industry some researches proved that the adoption of life-cycle cost compared to other cost estimation methods (Jiran et al.2013, Tannu and Kumar, 2014). Korpi and Ala-Risku (2008) buttressed that the life-cycle cost method is mainly popular because to its provides insights regarding the long-term affordability which makes it better when compared with other cost estimation methods. David & Anatoly (2006) emphasized that life-cycle cost minimises a lot of uncertainty for software projects because it reveals concealed costs which is significantly vital for SMEs not within the expertise of IT and possibly lacks the knowhow of estimating costs of software. Additionally, life-cycle cost plays an important role in software engineering as it can help to determine the success or failure of project execution through it elaborate cost analysis (Tripathi and Rai, 2016).

Chapter 5: Concluding Remarks

Mobile B2E apps are evolving issues when it comes to the implementation of new technologies in business organisation, delivering innovative services for several operations involving the customers and companies. For companies that have included such a mobile app within the project scope, the requirements elicitation process plays a vital role in determining the requirements and to build a foundation for the next or subsequent long-term decisions. This study presents an offer for a B2E company in the food sector with the aim of finding out the requirements for the project.

Moreover, the suitability of creating a mobile app for customers to use warranted the company to seek a to undertake a scoping study to find out the necessary requirements of developing an app that is outside the specialism of company. This study offers a comprehensive approach to expound several types of necessary project requirements meet the client's requirements. This comprehensive approach takes strength and basis from approved and tested methods backed with academic theory and industry case studies, that offer thorough applicable instructions and suggestions with respect to challenges the client is facing. The introduced methods can be adapted to the case of the client's specific requirements, so that the client obtains a scoping study that matches the business needs perfectly.

The case studies and experiences of previous software development projects presented in this study establish the suitability and validity of the methods to examine the stated functional, structural and resources requirement objectives and, also the multiple requirements of client to embark on the development of a mobile B2E app. Moreover, the close meetings and continuously communication with the client will help to identify discrepancies in client's requirement which can be altered to ensure optimal customisation of the intended mobile app that would be suitable for today's business environment.

Besides, the client can harness the help of Gantt-chart to track and evaluate project milestones and also identify the phase of the project where the client is so as to know what has been done and what is left within the timeframe specified. The information and vital results from this study enables the client to take the decision whether it worth it to continue with development of the mobile app itself or outsource it by buying a mobile app that can still

serve the client intended purpose. Arrival at this decision is aided by the outcomes of all conducted analyses that will ascertain if the client has the competences, resources and structure to create the app bearing the consequences of the likely project risks that occur.

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